

THE CONSTITUENTS OF *DIDYMOCARPUS PEDICELLATA*. PART IV. ISOLATION OF TWO NEW COLOURING MATTERS AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP TO PEDICIN.

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A second isomer of pedicin, pseudo-isopedicin, $C_{18}H_{18}O_6$, and a new colouring matter pedicidin, $C_{37}H_{36}O_{11}$, have been isolated from *D. pedicellata* and characterised. Pedicin can be converted into pseudo-isopedicin by Kostanecki's method and isopedicin was found to be transformed into pseudo-isopedicin on long storage. The mutual relationship of the three isomers of pedicin has been discussed. Pedicidin is probably a condensation product of the simpler colouring matters.

Sharma and Siddiqui (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 16, 1) have suggested the following tentative structures for pedicellin (I), pedicin (II), pedicinin (III) and isopedicin (IV).

The benzalcoumaranone structure for pedicinin was preferred to that of an isomeric flavanone because of its deep red colour and its colour reactions with ferric chloride, caustic alkali and sulphuric acid and because benzaldehyde was produced from it on treatment with alkali or permanganate. In view of the ease with which the five-membered ring in pedicinin ring is formed from the chalcone, pedicin, it appeared likely that isopedicin also should have a five and not a six-membered ring, hence it was deemed desirable to investigate this point more thoroughly by a closer study of pedicin and isopedicin.

With this object in view, the isolation of *isopedicin* in quantity was undertaken by a modified method in order to prevent its conversion to *pedicin* and also to facilitate the isolation of any other allied products, which might have been affected by the older method of separation (Siddiqui, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 705).

On working up 2 kg. of the drug by the new method (*vide* experimental), the following two new products, along with the previously described colouring matters, were obtained.

(1) *Pseudo-isopedicin*, $C_{15}H_9O_3(OMe)_3$, m. p. 126-28°, yield 0.45 %

(2) *Pedicidin*, $C_{30}H_{15}O_4(OMe)_7$, m.p. 190°, yield 0.12 % The molecular formulae are proposed on the basis of their C-H, OMe and M. W. values.

Pseudo-isopedicin was found to be saturated to bromine and like *isopedicin*, is easily converted into *pedicin* on treatment with dilute alkali at ordinary temperature. *Pedicin* could be reconverted into *pseudo-isopedicin* by Kostanecki's method (*Ber.*, 1904, **37**, 784) of converting chalcones to flavanones (or to the corresponding coumaranones). A two year old sample of *isopedicin*, which was originally noted to melt at 105° (Siddiqui, *loc. cit.*) now melts at 127° and showed no depression on admixture with the natural *pseudo-isopedicin* or the product obtained from *pedicin* by Kostanecki's method. The melting point of *isopedicin* was recorded for the air-dried substance and the possibility of its having been a hydrate of the higher melting *pseudo-isopedicin* is now definitely excluded by the fact that the latter's m.p. is unaffected after crystallisation from dilute alcohol. *Pseudo-isopedicin* gives the same colour reactions as *isopedicin* with alkali, sulphuric acid and ferric chloride.

It is probable that *isopedicin* (m.p. 105°) is racemised into *pseudo-isopedicin* on long storage and naturally racemic product is obtained when a ring-closure of *pedicin* is effected by Kostanecki's method. A more detailed investigation, now possible because of the easy accessibility of *pseudo-isopedicin*, will decide between the flavanone or coumaranone structure. The results will be soon communicated.

In regard to the higher molecular product, *pedicidin*, it has been noted that it takes up bromine, gives nearly the same colour reactions as *isopedicin* with alkali, sulphuric acid and ferric chloride and is converted into a deep red crystalline compound (m. p. 163-66°) by the action of nitric acid. It is too early to express an opinion as to the exact nature of *pedicidin* but its colour reactions and the presence of seven methoxyls suggest that it is probably formed by the condensation of two molecules of the simpler colouring matters. A detailed investigation is in progress.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Isolation of Pedicidin and Pseudo-isopedicin.—Coarsely powdered leaves (2 kg.) were successively soxhletted with petroleum ether (A) and ether (B) and the two extracts worked up separately as follows.

The crude colouring matter, which crystallised out on cooling the concentrated ethereal extract was washed thoroughly with a concentrated solution of sodium carbonate and the ethereal mother-liquor (M) was first washed with sodium carbonate solution and then with dilute sodium hydroxide. The combined carbonate extracts from above were acidified and extracted with ether and finally with chloroform. The ether and chloroform extracts yielded pedicinin as the least soluble fraction and crude *pseudo-isopedicin* was obtained from the mother-liquors of pedicinin. The portion insoluble in carbonate forming the major fraction of the crude colouring matter yielded pedicin, while the dilute caustic alkali extract, mentioned above, gave residual pedicin on acidification and extraction with ether and free stearic acid (*vide* Part III of this series).

The ethereal mother-liquor (M), which after washing with dilute caustic alkali contained only neutral substances, was washed with dilute acid and then with water and worked up according to the method described for the corresponding fraction in Part I (*loc. cit.*, p. 705). The crude pedicellin was obtained mostly before and partly after the removal of the essential oil by steam distillation. The second colouring matter, pedicidin, was isolated from the least soluble fraction of crude pedicellin, by fractional crystallisations. The ether extract (B) thus gave pedicinin (5g.), pedicin (4g.), pedicellin (6g.), more than half of *pseudo-isopedicin* (4.7g.), and the whole of the new product, pedicidin (2.5 g.). On being worked up in the above manner the petroleum ether extract (A) gave the whole of essential oils and fatty matter, the major part of pedicin (16 g.), about three-fourths of pedicellin (14 g.), very little of pedicinin and nearly half of the total *pseudo-isopedicin* (4.3 g.). No pedicidin could be isolated from this extract.

Pure *pseudo-isopedicin*, m. p. 126°, was obtained from the crude product on repeated crystallisations from a mixture of acetone and petroleum ether, which removed the persistent traces of pedicinin. Pedicidin was purified by successive crystallisations from chloroform, ethyl acetate and acetone.

Pseudo-iso-pedicin, $C_{18}H_{18}O_6$, is easily soluble in alcohol, chloroform and benzene, fairly so in ethyl acetate and acetone, sparingly soluble in ether and nearly insoluble in petroleum ether. It crystallises in straw coloured prismatic rods which dissolve in ammonia or in a

concentrated sodium carbonate solution with a yellow colour. In dilute sodium hydroxide it dissolves with a golden yellow colour, which soon turns brownish red and ultimately to deep red on standing. The change of colour from golden yellow to deep red evidently indicates its conversion to pedicin which takes place more rapidly in a 10% solution of sodium hydroxide. With sulphuric acid it gives deep red colour which vanishes on dilution. With ferric chloride its alcoholic solution gives an evanescent pale green colouration, which changes *via* light brownish red to deep reddish brown on standing. [Found : C, 65.44; H, 5.56; OMe, 27.54; M.W. (Rast), 320. $C_{15}H_{19}O_3(OMe)_3$ requires C, 65.5; H, 5.5; OMe, 28.1 per cent. M.W., 330).

Conversion of Pedicin into Pseudo-iso-pedicin.—A mixture of pedicin (0.3g.) in alcohol (5c.c.) and hydrochloric acid (*d* 1.16, 2.5c.c.) was refluxed for about 18 hours on the steam-bath. After removal of most of the alcohol, the mixture was diluted with water and extracted with ether and the ethereal solution washed with dilute sodium carbonate. The carbonate extract on acidification and extraction with ether yielded a small quantity of a reddish product which was not further examined. The ethereal layer yielded a light reddish yellow viscous mass, which on being successively treated with ether and cold acetone gave pale yellow prismatic rods (*ca* 0.2 g.), m.p. 125-26°, undepressed by *pseudo-isopedicin* and unaltered by crystallisation from dilute alcohol.

Pedicidin, $C_{37}H_{36}O_{11}$, is insoluble in ether and petroleum ether, soluble in chloroform, acetone and ethyl acetate in the hot and crystallises from these solvents in pale yellow elongated prisms, m. p. 190°. It gives a light brownish red reaction in alcohol and gives a reddish brown solution in concentrated sulphuric acid. [Found after drying at 100° in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : C, 68.08; H, 5.77; OMe, 33.85. M. W. (Rast), 731, (cryoscopic), 747; $C_{30}H_{15}O_4(OMe)_7$ requires C, 67.69; H, 5.48; OMe, 33.08 per cent. M.W., 656).

On addition of concentrated nitric acid to its glacial acetic acid solution it develops a dark red colour which quickly deepens, taking a violet tinge. The reaction mixture was immediately diluted with ice-water and extracted with ether; the residue from the ethereal solution crystallised on rubbing with alcohol, yielding deep red prismatic rods which after repeated washings with acetone on a porous plate, melted at 164-66 (shrinking from 161°).

